

THE INFLUENCE OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP EDUCATION AND MOTIVATION TO ENTREPRENEURIAL INTENTION OF YOUNG PROFESSIONALS IN COTABATO PROVINCE

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The Influence of Entrepreneurship Education and Motivation to Entrepreneurial Intention of Young Professionals in Cotabato Province

Mila Rose D. Javellana,* Novy Ly G. Monteverde, Jenny Rose C. Apolinario, Michelle S. Dela Torre, Edilyn S. Parde, Kleven Jake A. Villamor

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

Entrepreneurial Intention holds a significant influence in the process of entrepreneurship. It is the initial stage that motivates young professionals to initiate their ventures. The purpose of this research is to examine the relationship between entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial motivation as antecedents of entrepreneurial intention and how the Theory of Planned Behavior is being anchored during this study process. This quantitative study employs the descriptive correlation design to examine the 100 responses from young professionals with a business education degree in the province of Cotabato, Philippines. Snowball sampling technique and adaptive survey questionnaire are used, which ensures the precision of this study. Findings unveiled the profound importance of Entrepreneurship Education and Entrepreneurial Motivation with Entrepreneurial Intention reflected by its p-value of less than 0.05. Specifically, Entrepreneurship Education emerged as a key influencer of Entrepreneurial Intention, with a beta coefficient of 0.67 ($p < 0.00$). Respondents expressed a strong desire to start a business, encouragement and education are needed to translate intention into action. The study confirms a positive correlation between entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial motivation to entrepreneurial intention, suggesting that equipping young professionals with business knowledge and skills can significantly boost their confidence and entrepreneurial spirit. Entrepreneurship education appears to be the stronger influence compared to motivation, highlighting its crucial role in fostering future entrepreneurs and equipping them with knowledge by turning experience into action. The findings support Ajzen's theory, emphasizing the importance of education in shaping entrepreneurial intention.

Keywords: *entrepreneurial intention, entrepreneurship education, entrepreneurial motivation*

Introduction

Entrepreneurial intention plays a vital role in the entrepreneurship process, for it is the first stage to encourage young professionals to start their ventures. Recently, entrepreneurship has been recognized as an essential component for promoting long-term economic development. This strategy helps reduce unemployment, generate job opportunities, and assist the government in boosting economic growth (Shahzad et al., 2021). However, despite entrepreneurship having numerous benefits, it also presents many challenges. Some people face uncertainties when establishing their own business, which fails (Juárez et al., 2020).

There are several reasons why having an entrepreneurial intention is significant. Chipeta et al. (2017) believe it is crucial for economic development. Entrepreneurs launch new companies that boost the economy overall by producing jobs. Second, social mobility requires entrepreneurial intent. Regardless of socioeconomic standing or level of education, entrepreneurship can offer a road to success for people from all walks of life. Third, innovation requires entrepreneurial intent. Entrepreneurs frequently take charge of creating new goods and services.

Several contributing factors influence an entrepreneurial intention. This study focused on entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial motivation as influencers of entrepreneurial intention. Numerous studies concluded that these variables correlate with entrepreneurial intention. For instance, a survey by Aladejebi (2018) found that entrepreneurship education positively influences one's intentions to start a venture. Therefore, entrepreneurship education was identified as a factor in nurturing positive attitudes towards entrepreneurial intention. Maheshwari et al. (2022) discovered a significant positive association between entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial intentions. Many studies have demonstrated that entrepreneurship education significantly influences individual entrepreneurial intentions and knowingly enhances students' entrepreneurial intentions (Wu et al., 2022).

The drive to build business start-ups is vital to success. As a result, the researchers determined that entrepreneurial motivation is the major motivator and has a significant relationship for a person to gather information regarding entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial intention (Faghih et al., 2021). Driven entrepreneurs can better understand and sustain their desire to start a business and inspire people to believe in their concept. Educational institutions cannot engage individuals in entrepreneurial learning activities who are not motivated to start local enterprises. Thus, in a high level of task achievement, entrepreneurial motivation is key in developing individuals and has a positive relationship with entrepreneurial intention (Hassan et al., 2021). Furthermore, individuals who are motivated and brave enough to take risks in developing such firms require expertise and education tools to help them improve their entrepreneurial abilities (Kah et al., 2022).

There are some gaps in which researchers did not employ an effective evaluation procedure; instead, the researchers examined the procedural competencies in the field and concluded that different studies only provide subjective and temporary outcomes. The study lacks in anticipating and facing challenges as an entrepreneur, how to plan to overcome them, and the specific steps to prepare oneself

to be an entrepreneur. Thus, study on the relationship between entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial intention has yet to be conducted in the province of Cotabato. Most research attempted to clarify the factors influencing college students' entrepreneurial intentions. In this study, the focus will be on the young self-employed professionals. This research should gather reliable information on this topic and provide vital data. This study is unique and interesting because it contributes new perspectives to this study of literature by examining the roles of studying entrepreneurial intention and entrepreneurship education, which improves and provides access to fresh information or possibilities and has various effects that increase the chances of success by using this study to better understand their motivations, especially in our province.

The Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), introduced by Ajzen in 1991, offers a valuable lens through which to explore the relationship between entrepreneurship education, motivation, and the entrepreneurial intentions of young professionals. By assessing attitudes toward entrepreneurship, subjective norms within their social environment, and perceived behavioral control, researchers can gauge the influence of education programs on individuals' readiness to embark on entrepreneurial endeavors. Through TPB, the impact of entrepreneurship education on shaping attitudes, social influences, and beliefs about one's ability to engage in entrepreneurial activities can be elucidated, shedding light on the pathways through which motivation translates into concrete intentions. This integrated approach enables a nuanced understanding of the factors driving entrepreneurial behavior among young professionals, informing the design of targeted interventions and policies to foster a culture of entrepreneurship and innovation.

Research Questions

This study was conducted to determine the influence of entrepreneurship education and motivation to entrepreneurial orientation of young professionals. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of entrepreneurial intention, entrepreneurship education, and entrepreneurial motivation of young professionals in Cotabato Province?
2. Is there a significant relationship between:
 - 2.1. entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial intention; and
 - 2.2. entrepreneurial motivation and entrepreneurial intention?
3. Which between entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial motivation significantly influence the entrepreneurial intention of young professionals in Cotabato province?

Literature Review

Entrepreneurial Intention

Entrepreneurial intention is the desire of an individual or group to develop a new business idea and consider engaging in entrepreneurial activity (Fayolle et al., 2015). Knowledge and skills connected to entrepreneurship increase a person's willingness to launch a business (Lui et al., 2022). Entrepreneurial intention can help explain why some people prefer to start their own business before looking for opportunities or determining what kind of business to get involved in (Mangada, 2023).

Furthermore, entrepreneurial intention is a crucial beginning or critical step in becoming an entrepreneur, so developing behaviors that predict an increase in entrepreneurial intention should encourage students to take that step (Bell, 2019). The greater an individual's determination to engage in a particular behavior, the more likely it is that it will be carried out efficiently (Maresch et al., 2016). Entrepreneurial intention can be understood as a reflection of an individual's state of mind that prompts them to pursue self-employment rather than being employed (Karimi et al., 2016).

Research on economic development in Nigeria and entrepreneurship among aspiring business/management graduates used a sample of only 12.4% of the 500 final-year students. The respondents were randomly selected after graduation. Hence, graduates wanted to start their own business (Neneh, 2014). According to Aykol and Gurbuz (2009), in Turkey, among the young, educated public, gender, having entrepreneurial parents, subjective norms, perceived behavioral control, attitudes, favorable environmental conditions, and academic support were the drivers of entrepreneurial intention.

Furthermore, Abu Zahari's (2012) research in Singapore, which surveyed 5,326 undergraduate students, found that respondents were very interested in starting their own enterprises. Inadequate business expertise and perceived danger were the most significant barriers to intention. Gender, family business background, and academic level were the demographic characteristics that influenced intention. According to the data, citizenship, ethnicity, and family income status had no discernible influence on intention.

Numerous researchers have verified the connection between university students' entrepreneurial intentions and their choices to launch fresh businesses (Bae et al., 2014; Liñán & Fayolle, 2015). Promoting students' entrepreneurial intention, whose goal is to solve employment issues and generate social wealth through entrepreneurial activities, is becoming a more important focus of both government programs and university teaching (Ambad & Damit, 2016).

As stated by Ladd et al. (2018), intentional behavior is an entrepreneurial intention believed by college students to launch a new business after completing their education. However, business schools have frequently used business students or undefined populations to study entrepreneurial intention (Maresch et al., 2016). The expansion of entrepreneurship education's attention beyond its customary

concentration in business schools to other fields of education requires knowledge (Karlsson & Moberg, 2013).

Entrepreneurship Education

Entrepreneurship education is an educational program that discusses how to enhance knowledge, skills, attitudes, and individual character related to entrepreneurship (Wardana et al., 2020). Furthermore, it is a method rather than a process (Welsh et al., 2016). Also, entrepreneurship education generates innovative skills, which is a key factor for future progress (Wei et al., 2019).

Furthermore, it was mentioned in the study of Hassan et al. (2021) that entrepreneurship education may impart knowledge and promote entrepreneurship, which can help to develop entrepreneurial intention and turn it into actual behavior. For instance, activities that discuss and publish advanced knowledge, skills, attitudes, and characters that support students' success can help students learn and develop an understanding of entrepreneurship (Lv et al., 2021). Students can improve their critical thinking skills regarding entrepreneurship through the transition in education from a teacher-centered to a learner-centered approach (Wardana et al., 2020). Entrepreneurship courses equip students with essential teaching approaches such as business practice, company visits, and interviews with successful entrepreneurs. The teaching method, including contextual learning and real-life experiences, enhances entrepreneurship and entrepreneurial skills (Wardana et al., 2020).

The key to the development of the country is education since it plays an important role in sustainability (Aladejebi, 2018). Entrepreneurship education is increasing rapidly in tertiary institutions all over the world (Aladejebi, 2018). Government and academic institutions have given entrepreneurship education much attention, and how to assess and improve it has emerged as a crucial issue in the educational community (Liu et al., 2022). Graduates must change their mindset from job searching to job creation, as the government in our country cannot provide sufficient job opportunities for all tertiary-level graduates (Maheshwari et al., 2022). Researchers like Tengeh et al. (2015) believe that self-employment allows graduates to become job creators rather than job seekers since not everyone is cut out for the formal paid employment market.

According to Wei et al. (2019), entrepreneurs are not born but are developed by acquiring the necessary knowledge and skills for starting a new business. One of the primary objectives of entrepreneurial education is to ease the process and encourage the target population to become confident in starting a business (Dana et al., 2021). Many college graduates prefer to work for companies or in government, and only a few consider self-employment or becoming entrepreneurs because of a lack of confidence in their abilities and capital. (Herdjiono et al., 2017). Entrepreneurship education is crucial for entrepreneurs as it enhances their resource acquisition, innovative abilities, and personality while simultaneously building on mixed learning methods by integrating knowledge and value systems (Wei et al., 2019).

Over the last few years, universities have widely introduced entrepreneurship education to promote entrepreneurship among college students, and it is seen as one of the most important issues for higher education (Wu et al., 2022). Also, Entrepreneurship education can potentially influence students to engage in entrepreneurial activities. Entrepreneurship education aims to provide youth with practical knowledge and skills that will help them develop their character, attitude, and vision. Entrepreneurship education includes activities promoting entrepreneurial mindsets, attitudes, and abilities in ideas generation, startup, growth, and innovation (Aladejebi, 2018). Over the past two decades, the level of training in developed countries has increased, with entrepreneurial education being a key strategy to address socio-economic issues (Juarez et al., 2020). Entrepreneurship education motivates students to implement entrepreneurial ideas (Liu et al., 2022). Continuous learning and training are crucial for preparing the young population for jobs and new ventures (Juarez et al., 2020).

Entrepreneurship education can increase individuals' entrepreneurial intentions by enhancing entrepreneurial self-efficacy (Wu et al., 2022). In recent years, researchers have been paying more attention to entrepreneurial self-efficacy. Hassan et al. (2020) concluded in their research that entrepreneurship education in higher education strengthens the influence of recognition of opportunity on entrepreneurial intention. Furthermore, entrepreneurship education may be used to promote entrepreneurship (Hassan et al., 2020). It quickly spread throughout multiple higher education institutions worldwide and has successfully influenced students' intentions toward entrepreneurship, eventually developing into actual behavior (Hassan et al., 2020). The advantage of entrepreneurship-based education is that it helps students develop their entrepreneurial mindset, abilities, skills, and capacity to explore new entrepreneurial opportunities, which improves their intention to launch their businesses (Hassan et al., 2020).

Recent educational advancements emphasize the importance of promoting entrepreneurship due to its crucial role in developing positive attitudes, behaviors, mindsets, and intentions toward this field (Alshebami et al., 2020; Olugbola, 2017). Similarly, Wang et al. (2021) stated that entrepreneurship education equips students with the experiences, skills, and knowledge necessary for creating new businesses successfully. Kusumojanto et al. (2021) support this notion by suggesting that individuals who exhibit favorable dispositions toward entrepreneurship tend to perform well as entrepreneurs and view it not only as a means of survival but also as a way to achieve self-actualization.

Most earlier studies demonstrated that entrepreneurship can be taught, and education can be viewed as one of the most important tools for fostering entrepreneurial attitudes, intents, and competencies (Michelle & Tendai, 2016). Behavioral control was a significant factor in determining students' entrepreneurial motivation. For instance, students claimed that starting their own business was a means to boost prestige, fulfill aspirations, advance social standing, and pursue interests (Jena, 2020).

Entrepreneurial Motivation

Entrepreneurial motivation is a literature stating that starting a business might be forced upon a person due to their circumstances, such as poverty or unemployment, or it can be a conscious decision made out of a desire to take advantage of a perceived feasible business opportunity. These two distinct aspects are typically referred to as "push or necessity" and "pull or opportunity" factors, respectively (Ephrem et al., 2021). The motivation of an entrepreneur is a crucial factor in the decision to launch a business and has a significant impact on how well those businesses operate and succeed (Soraino, 2017). There is a perception that opportunity entrepreneurs, as opposed to necessity entrepreneurs, have a higher likelihood of success since they are motivated by the desire for achievement and greatness rather than money.

However, some entrepreneurs were dedicated to entrepreneurship in developing nations during the COVID-19 pandemic. According to Kariv et al. (2022), entrepreneurs were adaptable in responding to shocks during the pandemic, and female entrepreneurs were driven to launch their firms due to financial opportunities. Based on the preceding data, it is more difficult for college students to acquire their desired professions during a pandemic.

Entrepreneurial motivation in small and medium-sized businesses is typically characterized by risk-taking, innovation, and proactive attitudes (Presutti & Odorici, 2019). Additionally, sustainable entrepreneurs seek to use economic opportunities to change a market or industry to improve its environmental and social conditions. They evaluate their gains in financial and non-financial benefits, departing from traditional commercial entrepreneurship's notion of economic value (Jayaratne et al., 2019).

Entrepreneurship Education and Entrepreneurial Intentions

Entrepreneurial education is positively associated with students' entrepreneurial goals. Education can help business students develop entrepreneurial intentions by exposing them to successful entrepreneurs, encouraging hands-on experience, offering entrepreneurship-focused classes and workshops, providing access to funding and mentorship, fostering a supportive and inclusive environment, emphasizing the development of critical thinking and problem-solving skills, and encouraging continuous learning (Rindi et al., 2023).

Entrepreneurship education also positively affects students' intentions to become entrepreneurs and shapes their behaviors (Laila et al., 2023). It helps students understand business opportunities, utilize existing resources, and cope with uncertainty, developing the entrepreneurial attitude, adaptability, and creative thinking necessary to run their businesses (Atrup et al., 2023). Additionally, entrepreneurial education indirectly influences entrepreneurial intention by mediating entrepreneurial self-efficacy (Thi et al., 2023).

Moreover, the impact of entrepreneurial education on entrepreneurial intention extends beyond the classroom. Byun et al. (2021) examined the effects of entrepreneurship education on university students' entrepreneurial intention and found that exposure to entrepreneurship education programs positively influenced students' intention to pursue entrepreneurship even after graduation. This suggests that entrepreneurial education not only shapes individuals' immediate intentions but also has lasting effects on their entrepreneurial aspirations.

Entrepreneurial Motivation and Entrepreneurial Intention

Entrepreneurial motivation significantly impacts entrepreneurial intention (Nimitha et al., 2023). Studies show that motivation is crucial in shaping individuals' intentions to engage in entrepreneurial activities. Factors such as the need for achievement, autonomy, affiliation, power, subjective norms, attitude toward becoming an entrepreneur, and financial motive are identified as indicators of entrepreneurial motivation (Ananda et al., 2023).

Research by Obschonka et al. (2020) provides insights into the role of motivational factors, such as the need for achievement, autonomy, and risk-taking propensity, in shaping entrepreneurial intention among individuals. Their findings underscore the importance of intrinsic motivation, particularly the desire for achievement and autonomy, in driving individuals' intention to pursue entrepreneurial opportunities.

Methodology

Research Design

This study used descriptive correlational design. It is a type of research design that aims to systematically collect data to describe a phenomenon, occurrence, or population being studied. The main purpose is to provide a complete and accurate representation of the acquired data (Siedlecki, 2020). In quantitative studies, descriptive data illustrates individuals, events, or conditions. Correlational research is a non-experimental research approach that uses statistical analysis to investigate the link between two variables (Devi et al., 2023).

Descriptive statistics are used to describe the characteristics of the demographic profile, level/status/extent of entrepreneurial intention, entrepreneurship education, and entrepreneurial motivation in the three municipalities of Cotabato province. Correlation is used to determine the connections between entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial intention and entrepreneurial motivation and entrepreneurial intention. In addition, the correlational method helped determine the natural relationship and effects of variables on other variables as well.

Respondents

This study's respondents are young professionals with a degree in business education who have not yet engaged in business. According to DPE (2017), young professionals are aged 20 to 34. One hundred (100) young professionals were selected as respondents in the survey to collect data.

The snowball sampling technique was used to determine the respondents for this study. Snowball sampling is a non-random sampling strategy in which a few participants are used to recruit more participants to assist the researchers in participating in the study, increasing the sample size. To employ the snowball sampling method, the researchers identified individuals who fit the set criteria as respondents and then requested assistance by asking them to recommend individuals with the same characteristics.

Additionally, area sampling was utilized. Area sampling is used if an incomplete frame of reference is available. This approach is commonly used when the population and desired sample size are large (Simkus, 2023). The researchers collected a sample from a specific area or locale to represent the population, as collecting data from everyone in the population would be impossible. A sample from a particular area can better and faster represent the population with less time and effort.

The respondents include residents and young professionals with a business education degree who have not yet engaged in business or entrepreneurship and must be at least 21 to 30 years old. This study will exclude individuals not from the locale, who graduated from non-business-related courses or undergraduate programs, young professionals who already have a business, and those aged below 21 and above 30.

Instrument

This study used an adapted survey questionnaire. A part of the survey conducted by previous researchers has been adapted and slightly modified to ensure the precision of this study. The instrument was composed of four parts. The first part gathered the demographic profile of the respondents.

The second part of the survey questionnaire measures entrepreneurial intention. Ahmad et al. (2023) studied this question: "Do entrepreneurial self-efficacy, entrepreneurial motivation, and family support enhance entrepreneurial intention? The mediating role of entrepreneurial education". Furthermore, the third part of the study utilized the measurement of entrepreneurship education developed by Aliyu (2024) in the study "Assessment of Entrepreneurial Education as a Strategy for Developing Entrepreneurial Intention Amongst University Students in North-East Nigeria."

Additionally, the last part measured entrepreneurial motivation. The instrument was adapted from the study of Garba and Adamu (2023) in their study "The Influence of Entrepreneurship Education, Entrepreneurial Motivation and Creativity on Entrepreneurial Intention: The Mediating Role of Self-Efficacy." These instruments have a Cronbach alpha value of more than .70 and were rated using the 5-point Likert Scale where 1 - Strongly Disagree, 2 - Disagree, 3 - Fairly Agree, 4 - Agree, and 5 - Strongly Agree.

Adapting a survey instrument offers researchers several key advantages. By leveraging validated scales and measures from existing instruments, researchers can ensure the validity and reliability of their collected data. This approach also facilitates comparability with previous studies, enabling cross-study comparisons and meta-analyses. Additionally, using established measures allows researchers to benefit from existing quality assurance processes, enhancing the accuracy and reliability of their data.

In this study, the adapted instrument's statements were carefully modified to contextualize the instrument to the specific locale and respondents. This tailoring ensures the collection of data that is most relevant and meaningful to the research questions. A pilot test was conducted with thirty respondents to refine the instrument further, providing valuable feedback for final adjustments. The pilot test generated a Cronbach alpha value of more than 0.70, making the instrument reliable.

Procedure

Before the research data collection began, a communication letter requesting approval to carry out the research study on behalf of Southern Baptist College was provided and addressed to the Dean of the College of Business Education of Southern Baptist College.

A comprehensive survey was designed and implemented using Google Forms to glean insights into the perspectives of young professionals. Upon finalizing the survey instrument, a shareable link was generated and strategically disseminated to the young professional organizations through Facebook Messenger and email addresses. Accompanying the link was a brief explanation of the study's objectives and a compelling call to action, underscoring the importance of their participation in contributing to valuable research findings.

A reasonable timeframe for survey completion was established, two weeks, and the researchers diligently monitored the incoming responses through Google Forms' intuitive analytics dashboard. This real-time feedback mechanism allowed for the identification of any potential issues or trends early on, ensuring the integrity of the data collection process.

Upon the conclusion of the response window, the amassed data was securely downloaded in a compatible format, paving the way for in-depth analysis and the subsequent extraction of meaningful insights that would inform the study's conclusions and recommendations.

Ethical Considerations

The researchers adhered to the ten dimensions of research ethics: social value, informed consent, vulnerability issues, risk-benefit ratio, privacy and confidentiality of information, justice, transparency, researcher qualifications, adequacy of facilities, and community involvement. The confidentiality of information was maintained throughout the research process in strict accordance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012 (Republic Act 10173). This law mandates transparency, legitimate purpose, and proportionality in collecting, retaining, and processing personal information, all of which were diligently observed by the researchers.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 presents the level of entrepreneurial intention, entrepreneurship education, and entrepreneurial motivation of young professionals in Cotabato province. It can be gleaned from the table that the level of entrepreneurial intention of young professionals is high. The overall mean score of 3.99 indicates that the young professionals in Cotabato province generally exhibit a strong inclination towards entrepreneurship. This suggests that they possess a favorable attitude toward starting and running their own businesses. The individual item scores further reveal that respondents are particularly determined to create a firm in the future and are serious about starting one. However, even though it is noted that while they have a positive outlook, there might be some reservations or perceived challenges in their journey towards becoming entrepreneurs.

On the other hand, the survey revealed that the entrepreneurship education of young professionals is high. The overall positive perception of entrepreneurship education, as evidenced by the high mean score of 3.59, suggests that respondents value and appreciate the entrepreneurial knowledge and insights they have gained. A discrepancy was noted, indicating a potential gap between theoretical understanding and practical skills, suggesting a need to focus on developing the concrete competencies and capabilities required for successful entrepreneurial ventures. By addressing this gap, educational programs can better equip aspiring entrepreneurs with the tools they need to translate their positive attitudes and intentions into tangible business outcomes.

Finally, it was revealed that the overall mean score of 3.18, categorized as "moderate," suggests that the respondents' entrepreneurial motivation is relatively balanced. While they are motivated by factors such as increasing their income, implementing innovative ideas, and bringing positive change, they are less driven by necessity or external influences like friends' suggestions or government policies. The high scores for items related to personal and societal benefits highlight the intrinsic motivation and desire for self-improvement among the respondents. However, the moderate scores for items related to external factors and necessity suggest that addressing these concerns could further enhance entrepreneurial motivation.

The findings of this study support the conclusion made by Neneh (2014) that business and management graduates want to start their own businesses. Additionally, according to Abu Zahari's (2012) research in Singapore, there is a high degree of interest among business students in starting their own businesses. Furthermore, entrepreneurship education is crucial for entrepreneurs as it enhances their resource acquisition, innovative abilities, and personality (Wei et al., 2019).

Moreover, according to a study, prior experience significantly influences entrepreneurial intention. Therefore, by providing the necessary entrepreneurial knowledge and practices, entrepreneurial education may increase entrepreneurial self-efficacy, which may impact entrepreneurial intention (Wu et al., 2022).

On the other hand, the study of Vrontis et al. (2021) indicates moderate entrepreneurial motivation among young professionals. This can be attributed to access to financing, government, and family support. Moreover, research identified financial gain, professional autonomy, and creativity as primary motivators for young entrepreneurs. These factors contribute to a moderate yet growing interest in entrepreneurship among young professionals (Sait & Kasmir, 2023).

Table 1. *Level of Entrepreneurial Intention, Entrepreneurship Education and Entrepreneurial Motivation*

Variables	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Entrepreneurial Intention	0.93	3.99	High
Entrepreneurship Education	0.90	3.59	High
Entrepreneurial Motivation	1.02	3.18	Moderate

Correlation Between Variables

The correlation analysis revealed a strong positive relationship between entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial intention. A p-value less than 0.05 indicates statistical significance, suggesting that the observed correlation is unlikely to be due to chance. An r-value of 0.71 demonstrates a substantial positive association, implying that as young professionals in Cotabato Province receive more entrepreneurship education, they are more likely to express a desire to start their own businesses.

The second correlation analysis also found a significant positive relationship between entrepreneurial motivation and entrepreneurial intention. While the r-value of 0.41 is lower than the previous correlation, it still indicates a moderately strong positive association. This suggests that young professionals with higher levels of entrepreneurial motivation are more likely to have entrepreneurial

intentions.

When considering both correlations, it becomes evident that entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial motivation play crucial roles in shaping entrepreneurial intentions among young professionals in Cotabato Province. Entrepreneurship education seems to be particularly influential, as it has a stronger correlation with entrepreneurial intention. However, entrepreneurial motivation also plays a significant role, as it can amplify the impact of entrepreneurship education.

These findings have important implications for policymakers and educators in Cotabato Province. By investing in quality entrepreneurship education programs and fostering entrepreneurial motivation, they can effectively encourage young professionals to pursue entrepreneurial ventures. Furthermore, these results highlight the need for a comprehensive approach that combines both education and motivation to maximize the potential for entrepreneurial growth.

Table 2. Relationship among Variables

Variables Paired	r	P	Remarks
Entrepreneurship Education and Entrepreneurial Intention	.71	.00	Significant
Entrepreneurial Motivation and Entrepreneurial Intention	.41	.00	Significant

The study's findings affirm the conclusions reached by Hassan et al. (2020) that indicate a positive correlation between entrepreneurship education and enhanced entrepreneurial intention and skills. Wang et al. (2021) have similarly reported that numerous studies demonstrate a significant influence between the extent of entrepreneurship education received and individual entrepreneurial intentions. Lv et al. (2021) further support these claims, indicating higher levels of entrepreneurial intention among those who have undergone entrepreneurship education. Thus, we conclude that increasing access to quality entrepreneurship education will lead to an improvement in the levels of entrepreneurial intention.

The study's findings align with those of Faghih et al. (2021), who determined a substantial correlation between entrepreneurial motivation and entrepreneurship education. Furthermore, Schlepphorst et al. (2020) observed that an individual's entrepreneurial intention is influenced by various motives, ultimately driving them toward tangible action. This study proves that if the higher the entrepreneurial motivation is, then the entrepreneurial intentions also increase.

Influencers of Entrepreneurial Intention

The regression analysis further supports the findings from the correlation analysis. Entrepreneurship education emerges as a significant predictor of entrepreneurial intention, with a beta coefficient of .67 ($p < .00$). This indicates that a one-unit increase in entrepreneurship education is associated with a .67 unit increase in entrepreneurial intention. On the other hand, entrepreneurial motivation is not a significant predictor in this model, suggesting that its influence on intention might be mediated by other factors or that its impact is less direct compared to education. The overall model explains 51% of the variance in entrepreneurial intention ($R^2 = .51$), indicating a reasonably good fit.

Table 3. Regression Result

Influencers of Entrepreneurial Intention	B	p	t	Remarks
Entrepreneurship Education	.67	.00	8.18	Significant
Entrepreneurial Motivation	.12	.21	1.26	Not Significant
$r^2 = .51$				
$F = 50.01$				
$p = .00$				

The regression analysis underscores the pivotal role of entrepreneurship education in shaping entrepreneurial intentions. The significant positive beta coefficient of .67 indicates a strong and direct relationship between increased exposure to entrepreneurship education and a heightened likelihood of individuals pursuing entrepreneurial ventures. This finding has far-reaching implications for various stakeholders.

For policymakers, it reinforces the importance of investing in entrepreneurship education at all levels of education. By integrating entrepreneurship curricula into schools and universities, governments can cultivate a pipeline of future entrepreneurs and foster economic growth. Educational institutions can enhance their entrepreneurship programs by offering specialized courses, workshops, and mentorship opportunities, providing students with practical skills and networking possibilities. Businesses can also benefit by

investing in entrepreneurship training for their employees, fostering a culture of innovation, and encouraging employees to explore entrepreneurial ventures. Ultimately, the positive impact of entrepreneurship education extends beyond individual intentions and contributes to the overall entrepreneurial ecosystem.

These findings resonate with the conclusion of a study involving 347 students in China, which found that entrepreneurship education positively predicts college students' entrepreneurial intentions (Fan & Wang, 2024). Similarly, research in the UK indicated that psychological capital partially mediates the influence of entrepreneurship education on entrepreneurial intention, emphasizing the roles of hope and self-efficacy (Haddoud et al., 2024).

Furthermore, in Malaysia, a study revealed that entrepreneurship education significantly influenced entrepreneurial intention, particularly among social science students, highlighting the importance of cognitive factors like personal attitude and perceived behavioral control (Mahmood et al., 2024).

Conclusions

Based on the findings, young professionals in Cotabato province demonstrate a strong entrepreneurial inclination, coupled with a positive perception of entrepreneurship education and a moderate level of entrepreneurial motivation. These results align with previous research and highlight the importance of providing targeted support to help these individuals translate their positive intentions into successful entrepreneurial ventures. By addressing potential gaps in entrepreneurial motivation and practical skills, policymakers, educational institutions, and businesses can create a conducive environment for entrepreneurship and foster economic growth in the region.

The correlation analysis reveals a strong positive relationship between entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial intention, suggesting that increased exposure to entrepreneurship education significantly enhances the likelihood of young professionals in Cotabato Province pursuing entrepreneurial ventures. Additionally, while the correlation between entrepreneurial motivation and entrepreneurial intention is moderately strong, it further emphasizes the importance of both factors in shaping entrepreneurial aspirations.

Furthermore, the study provides compelling evidence that entrepreneurship education is a significant predictor of entrepreneurial intention, surpassing the influence of entrepreneurial motivation in this specific model. The result highlights the direct and powerful relationship between increased exposure to entrepreneurship education and a heightened likelihood of individuals pursuing entrepreneurial ventures.

This finding has far-reaching implications for various stakeholders. Policymakers should prioritize the integration of entrepreneurship education into educational curricula at all levels to foster a culture of entrepreneurship and drive economic growth. Educational institutions can enhance their entrepreneurship programs to equip students with the necessary skills and knowledge, including practical experience and networking opportunities. Businesses can benefit by investing in entrepreneurship training for their employees, fostering a culture of innovation and encouraging entrepreneurial ventures.

While entrepreneurial motivation may also play a role in shaping entrepreneurial intentions, the regression analysis suggests that its impact might be mediated by other factors or that its influence is less direct compared to entrepreneurship education. Further research is needed to explore the complex interplay between these variables and to identify additional factors that may influence entrepreneurial intentions.

The findings of this study align with the Theory of Planned Behavior, suggesting that individuals' intentions to engage in entrepreneurial activities are influenced by their attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control. The positive perception of entrepreneurship education, supportive social pressures, and moderate levels of entrepreneurial motivation collectively contribute to the development of entrepreneurial intentions among young professionals in Cotabato Province.

The researchers recommend that universities and other educational institutions prioritize developing students' understanding of entrepreneurship beyond mere interest or entertainment. While these factors are important motivators, passion and practical knowledge are equally crucial for successful entrepreneurship. By assisting students in discovering their passions and aligning them with potential business opportunities and by providing exposure to real-life experiences, educational institutions can enhance students' understanding and motivation toward entrepreneurship. Future studies should investigate additional factors that influence entrepreneurial intentions beyond entrepreneurship education and motivation to gain a broader understanding of the forces driving people's entrepreneurial aspirations and to support economic development.

References

- Abbassi, R., & Sta, N. (2019). The Effect of self-esteem, entrepreneurship education, and entrepreneurial tradition of the family on the entrepreneurial intention among students. *Journal of Business and Management Research*.
- Ahmed I., Nawaz M. M., Ramzan M. (2012). Do external factors influence students' entrepreneurial inclination? An evidence-based approach.

- Aladejebi, O. (2018). The effect of entrepreneurship education on entrepreneurial intention among tertiary institutions in Nigeria. *Journal of Small Business and Entrepreneurship Development*.
- ALIYU, I. (2024). Assessment of Entrepreneurial Education as a Strategy for Developing Entrepreneurial Intention Amongst University Students in North-East Nigeria.
- Amofah, K., Saladrignes, R. (2022). Impact of attitude towards entrepreneurship education and role models on entrepreneurial intention.
- Arrighetti, A, Caricati, L, Landini, F, & Monacelli, N. (2013). Explaining entrepreneurial orientation among university students
- Audretsch, D. B., Belitski, M., & Desai, S. (2015b). Entrepreneurship and economic development in cities. *The Annals of Regional Science*.
- Bae, T. J., Qian, S., Miao, C., & Fiet, J. O. (2014). The Relationship between Entrepreneurship Education and Entrepreneurial Intentions: A Meta-Analytic Review. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*.
- Baier-Fuentes H., Merigó J. M., Amorós J. E., Gavieri-Martin M. (2019). International entrepreneurship: a bibliometric overview.
- Burchi A, Włodarczyk B, Szturo M, Martelli D (2021) The effects of financial literacy on sustainable entrepreneurship.
- Byun, G., Lee, D., & Park, S. (2021). The effects of entrepreneurship education on entrepreneurial intention: A longitudinal study. *Education and Training*, 63(4), 456–471.
- Cabeza-Ramírez L. J., Sanchez-Cañizares S. M., Fuentes-García F. J. (2017). Entrepreneurship as a dynamic field of study: a bibliometric analysis of research output.
- Caiazza, R., Richardson, A., & Audretsch, D. B. (2015). Knowledge effects on competitiveness: from firms to regional advantage. *The Journal of Technology Transfer*.
- Cardella GM, Hernández-Sánchez BR and Sánchez García JC (2020) Entrepreneurship and Family Role: A Systematic Review of a Growing Research.
- Dawson A., Sharma P., Irving P. G., Marcus J., Chirico F. (2015). Predictors of later generation family members' commitment to family enterprises.
- De Massis A., Kotlar J., Chua J., Chrisman J. J. (2014). Ability and willingness as sufficiency conditions for family-oriented particularistic behavior: implications for theory and empirical studies.
- Diandra, D., & Azmy, A. (2020). Understanding definition of entrepreneurship. *International Journal of Management, Accounting and Economics*.
- Edelman L. F., Manolova T., Shirokova G., Tsukanova T. (2016). The impact of family support on young entrepreneurs' start-up activities.
- Ezeuduji, I. O., & Ntshangase, S. D. (2017). Entrepreneurial inclination: South African youth's mental attitude towards starting tourism business. *Journal of Economics and Behavioral Studies*.
- Fan, J., Wang, J. (2024). How entrepreneurship education affects college students' entrepreneurial intention: Samples from China. *Heliyon*, doi: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e30776
- Fatoki, O., & Oni, O. (2014). Students' perception of the effectiveness of entrepreneurship education at a South African University. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*.
- Fernández Robin C., Santander Astorga P., Yáñez Martínez D. (2017). Entrepreneurial constraints on women in Chile: an empirical approach.
- Fini, R, Meoli, A, Sobrero, M, Ghiselli, S and Ferrante, F. (2016) Student Entrepreneurship: Demographics, Competences and Obstacles. Technical Report - Almalaurea Consortium Ferrante,
- Garba, M. M., & Adamu, I. (2023). The Influence of Entrepreneurship Education, Entrepreneurial Motivation and Creativity on Entrepreneurial Intention: The Mediating Role of Self-Efficacy. *Sustainable Governance, Citizenship and National Development*, 563.
- Gautam, M. K., & Singh, D. S. K. (2015). Entrepreneurship education: concept, characteristics, and implications for teacher education.
- Haase, H., & Lautenschläger, A. (2021). Digital Entrepreneurial Intention: A Literature Review and Research Agenda. In *International Conference on Business Informatics Research* (pp. 69-84). Springer, Cham
- Haddoud, M. Y., Nowiński W., Laouiti R., Onjewu, A. (2024). Entrepreneurial implementation intention: The role of psychological capital and entrepreneurship education. *The International Journal of Management Education*, doi: 10.1016/j.ijme.2024.100982

- Hahn, D., Minola, T., Bosio, G., and Cassia, L. (2019). The impact of entrepreneurship education on university students' entrepreneurial skills: a family embeddedness perspective. *Small Bus. Econ.*
- Hassan, A., Saleem, I., Anwar, I., & Hussain, S. A. (2020). Entrepreneurial intention of Indian university students: the role of opportunity recognition and entrepreneurship education. *Education+ Training.*
- Ho, M.-H. R., Uy, M. A., Kang, B. N. Y., & Chan, K.-Y. (2018). Impact of entrepreneurship training on entrepreneurial efficacy and alertness among adolescent youth.
- Iqbal N, Khan A, Gill AS, Abbas Q (2020) Nexus between sustainable entrepreneurship and environmental pollution: evidence from developing economy.
- Iwu, C. G., Opute, P. A., Nchu, R., Eresia-Eke, C., Tengeh, R. K., Jaiyeoba, O., & Aliyu, O. A. (2021). Entrepreneurship education, curriculum and lecturer-competency as antecedents of student entrepreneurial intention. *The International Journal of Management Education.*
- Jena, R. K. (2020). Measuring the impact of business management Student's attitude towards entrepreneurship education on entrepreneurial intention: A case study. *Computers in Human Behavior.*
- Jiatong, W., Murad, M., Bajun, F., Tufail, M. S., Mirza, F., & Rafiq, M. (2021). Impact of entrepreneurial education, mindset, and creativity on entrepreneurial intention: mediating role of entrepreneurial self-efficacy. *Frontiers in Psychology.*
- Karimi, S., Biemans, H.J.A., Lans, T., Chizari, M. and Mulder, M. (2016), "The impact of entrepreneurship education: a study of Iranian students' entrepreneurial intentions and opportunity identification", *Journal of Small Business Management*
- Kusumojanto, D. D., Wibowo, A., Kustiandi, J., & Narmaditya, B. S. (2021). Do entrepreneurship education and environment promote students' entrepreneurial intention? The role of entrepreneurial attitude. *Cogent Education.*
- Ladd, T., P. Hind, and J. Lawrence. 2018. "Entrepreneurial Orientation, Waynesian Selfefficacy for Searching and Marshaling, and Intention across Gender and Region of Origin." *Journal of Small Business & Entrepreneurship*
- Laila, Cekule., Andrejs, Cekuls., Margarita, Dunska. (2023). The role of education in fostering entrepreneurial intentions among business students. doi: 10.4995/head23.2023.16159
- Liu Y, Li M, Li X and Zeng J (2022) Entrepreneurship education on entrepreneurial intention: The moderating role of the personality and family economic status. *Front. Psychol.*
- López-Fernández M. C., Serrano-Bedia A. M., Pérez-Pérez M. (2015). Entrepreneurship and family firm research: a bibliometric analysis of an emerging field. *J. Small Bus.*
- Ludi Wishnu Wardana, Bagus Shandy Narmaditya, Agus Wibowo, Angga Martha Mahendra, Nyuherno Aris Wibowo, Gleydis Harwida, Arip Nur Rohman, (2020). The impact of entrepreneurship education and students' entrepreneurial mindset: the mediating role of attitude and self-efficacy.
- Lv Y., Chen Y., Sha Y., Wang J., An L., Chen T., Huang X., Huang Y., Huang L., (2021) How Entrepreneurship Education at Universities Influences Entrepreneurial Intention: Mediating Effect Based on Entrepreneurial Competence.
- Mahmood, R., Ahmand, Z., Zahari, A., Fuza, Z., Azwani, N., Azmin, M. (2024). Entrepreneurship Education Position and Entrepreneurial Intention: The Perception of Malaysian Undergraduate Students. *International Journal of Social Science Research*, 12(2):119-119. doi: 10.5296/ijssr.v12i2.21534
- Mangada, E. (2023). Entrepreneurial Attitudes, Intentions and Motivations among University Students in the National Capital Region. *Advances in Social Sciences Research Journal*
- Maresch, D., Harms, R., Kailer, N. and Wimmer-Wurm, B. (2016), "The impact of entrepreneurship education on the entrepreneurial intention of students in science and engineering versus business studies university programs", *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*
- Miao Y, Du R, Ou CX (2022) Guanxi circles and light entrepreneurship in social commerce: the roles of mass entrepreneurship climate and technology affordances microcredit entrepreneurs: Empirical evidence from Malaysia. *International Journal of Business and Social Science.*
- Obschonka, M., Fisch, C., Boyd, R. L., Slaughter, J. E., McCann, S. J., & Barker, J. (2020). Testing regional models of entrepreneurial intentions in the USA: Evidence from a representative sample of the adult population. *Small Business Economics*, 54(2), 487-514
- OECD (2017), *Entrepreneurship at a Glance*, OECD Publishing, Paris.
- Okuwhere MP, Tafamel AE (2022) Coronavirus (COVID-19) and entrepreneurship in Africa: challenges and opportunities for small

and medium enterprises innovation.

Otache, I. (2019). Entrepreneurship education and undergraduate students' self-and paid-employment intentions: A conceptual framework. *Education+ Training*.

Overbeke K. K., Bilimoria D., Perelli S. (2013). The dearth of daughter successors in family businesses: gendered norms, blindness to possibility, and invisibility. *J. Fam. Bus.*

Purwati A., Hamzah M., Suhermin S. (2020). Entrepreneurship education and its impact on students' intention to pursue entrepreneurship.

Rofa, N., & Ngah, R. (2022). Entrepreneurial Personality Traits Towards Entrepreneurial Potential of TVET Students in Malaysia: A PLS-SEM Approach.

Roper, S., Love, J. H., & Bonner, K. (2017). Firms' knowledge search and local knowledge externalities in innovation performance. *Research Policy*.

Sait S., Kasmir L. (2023). A Walk on Entrepreneurial Path: A Journey of Young Entrepreneurs. doi: 10.21203/rs.3.rs-3320065/v1

Saoula, O., Shamim, A., Ahmad, M. J., & Abid, M. F. (2023). Do entrepreneurial self-efficacy, entrepreneurial motivation, and family support enhance entrepreneurial intention? The mediating role of entrepreneurial education. *Asia Pacific Journal of Innovation and Entrepreneurship*

Shah, I. A., Amjed, S., & Jaboob, S. (2020). The moderating role of entrepreneurship education in shaping entrepreneurial intentions. *Journal of Economic Structures*.

Tanpoco (2022). The Effects of Pre-University Entrepreneurship education on Entrepreneurial Intention as Mediated by Acquired competencies and Mindset. *Journal of Positive School Psychology*.

Tavassoli, S., Bengtsson, L., & Karlsson, C. (2017). Strategic entrepreneurship and knowledge spillovers: Spatial and aspatial perspectives. *International Entrepreneurship and Management Journal*

Tengeh, R. K., Iwu, C. G., & Nchu, R. M. (2015). The embeddedness of entrepreneurship education in the curricula of non-business university programmes: Preliminary evidence from South African Universities of Technology.

Tian, H., Akhtar, S., Qureshi, N. A., & Iqbal, S. (2022). Predictors of entrepreneurial intentions: The role of prior business experience, opportunity recognition, and entrepreneurial education. *Frontiers in Psychology*.

Vrontis, D., Chaarani H., Nemar S., EL-Abiad Z., Ali R., Trichina E. (2021). The motivation behind an international entrepreneurial career after first employment experience. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behaviour & Research*, doi: 10.1108/IJEER-06-2021-0498

Wardana, L. W., Narmaditya, B. S., Wibowo, A., Mahendra, A. M., Wibowo, N. A., Harwida, G., & Rohman, A. N. (2020). The impact of entrepreneurship education and students' entrepreneurial mindset: the mediating role of attitude and self-efficacy. *Heliyon*.

Welsh, D. H., Tullar, W. L., & Nemati, H. (2016). Entrepreneurship education: Process, method, or both?. *Journal of Innovation & Knowledge*.

Welter, F., Baker, T., & Wirsching, K. (2019). Three waves and counting: the rising tide of contextualization in entrepreneurship research. *Small Business Economics*

West, J., & Bogers, M. (2014). Leveraging external sources of innovation: A review of research on open innovation. *Journal of Product Innovation Management*

Wiani, A., Ahman, E., & Machmud, A. (2018). Effect of family environment on interest in entrepreneurship students smk in subang regency. *Oikos: Jurnal Ekonomi dan Pendidikan Ekonomi*.

Wu, L., Jiang, S., Wang, X., Yu, L., Wang, Y., Pan, H. (2022) Entrepreneurship Education and Entrepreneurial Intentions of College Students: The Mediating Role of Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy and the Moderating Role of Entrepreneurial Competition Experience.

Yan, J., Huang, T., & Xiao, Y. (2023). Assessing the impact of entrepreneurial education activity on entrepreneurial intention and behavior: role of behavioral entrepreneurial mindset. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*.

Zellweger T. (2017). *Managing the Family Business: Theory and Practice*. Cheltenham: Edward Elgar.

Zhou, B., Zeng, X., Jiang, L., & Xue, B. (2020). High-quality economic growth under the influence of technological innovation preference in China: A numerical simulation from the government financial perspective. *Structural Change and Economic Dynamics*.

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Mila Rose D. Javellana

Southern Baptist College – Philippines

Novy Ly G. Monteverde

Southern Baptist College – Philippines

Jenny Rose C. Apolinario

Southern Baptist College – Philippines

Michelle S. Dela Torre

Southern Baptist College – Philippines

Edilyn S. Parde

Southern Baptist College – Philippines

Kleven Jake A. Villamor, DBM, CRS

Southern Baptist College – Philippines